

A Study to Estimate Oxidative Stress and Antioxidant Status in Tropical Chronic Pancreatitis (TCP) and Alcoholic Chronic Pancreatitis (ACP) and Correlate with Zinc Status

Saurabh Raj¹, Deepak², Pankaj Kumar³, Amit Kumar⁴, Shivendra Tiwari⁵, Manish Kumar⁶

¹(DrNB) Academic Senior Resident, Department of Gastroenterology, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India

²Consultant, Gastroenterologist, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India

³Consultant Gastroenterologist, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India

⁴(DrNB) Academic Senior Resident, Department of Gastroenterology, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India

⁵(DrNB) Academic Senior Resident, Department of Gastroenterology, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India

⁶(DrNB) Academic Senior Resident, Department of Gastroenterology, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 13-03-2024 Revised: 10-04-2024 / Accepted: 08-05-2024

Corresponding author: Dr. Saurabh Raj

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to estimate oxidative stress and antioxidant status in tropical chronic pancreatitis (TCP) and alcoholic chronic pancreatitis (ACP) and correlate with zinc status.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the Department of Gastroenterology, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India and Chronic pancreatitis patients were recruited for the study and was diagnosed on the basis of presence of pancreatic calcification (US/CT) and/or parenchymal or ductal changes on imaging. 100 patients were included in the study. This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee and written informed consent was obtained from the subjects before enrollment.

Results: Of the 100 patients, there were 50 TCP patients and 50 ACP patients. The mean age of all CP patients was comparable with the age of controls; however, TCP patients were younger than ACP patients. The mean body mass index was comparable in all three groups. The erythrocyte GSH, GPx, SOD, and plasma vitamin C levels were lower, and erythrocyte TBARS was higher in both TCP and ACP patients as compared to healthy controls. Plasma vitamin C was lower whereas, erythrocyte TBARS was higher in TCP patients as compared to ACP patients. Erythrocyte GSH level was significantly low in ACP as compared to TCP patients. We found lower values of erythrocyte GSH, GPx, SOD, and plasma vitamin C and higher erythrocyte TBARS in both diabetic and non-diabetic CP patients as compared to healthy controls. However, we did not find differences between diabetic and non-diabetic TCP patients or between diabetic and non-diabetic ACP patients.

Conclusion: The study corroborates the role of oxidative stress in CP and suggests some differences in oxidative status in TCP and ACP patients. Zinc deficiency appears to affect oxidative status in CP patients.

Keywords: estimate oxidative stress, antioxidant status, tropical chronic pancreatitis, alcoholic chronic pancreatitis (ACP), zinc status

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The progressive and irreversible destruction to the pancreatic parenchyma and ductal anatomy in chronic pancreatitis (CP) patients is often accompanied by severe, intractable abdominal pain. Histologically, CP entails excessive deposition of collagen by pancreatic stellate cells (PSCs), loss of

acinar and islet cells, and infiltration of the tissue by inflammatory cells and molecules. [1,2] Functional manifestations, usually occurring later in the disease after substantial damage is sustained to pancreatic tissues, include exocrine pancreatic insufficiency and loss of endocrine function, leading to diabetes.

Quality of life is reduced in CP patients, with 85% of patients experiencing pain. [3] CP-induced abdominal pain is deep and internal, ranging in severity from mild to unbearable. Such pain often leads to unemployment due to disability, frequent hospitalizations, excessive use of medications, including narcotics, and multiple medical and surgical interventions.²

Risk factors for CP are categorized by the TIGAR-O classification system as toxic-metabolic, idiopathic, genetic, autoimmune, recurrent severe acute pancreatitis, or obstructive. Toxic and metabolic factors include alcohol, tobacco, and some medications and toxins. Alcohol use is reported to precede 55–80% of CP cases; however, only 10% of heavy alcohol drinkers suffer from pancreatic disease. [4] This indicates the involvement of other risk factors in the development of alcohol-associated CP. In fact, most cases of CP probably result from a combination of risk factors. Up to 25% of CP cases are of unknown cause and are, thus, classified as idiopathic. [5]

Zinc is a key element in numerous proteins and plays an important role in essential cell functions such as defense against free radicals and DNA damage repair. [6] Approximately 10% to 40% of dietary zinc is absorbed in the small bowel and 0.5 to 1.0 mg/day is secreted into the biliary tract followed by passing the small and large bowel. [7] Pathophysiology of zinc deficiency in patients with chronic pancreatitis (CP) is not fully elucidated. It has been proposed that decreased secretion of binding proteins in the pancreatic juice explain compromised absorption of zinc in pancreatic exocrine insufficiency (PEI). [8] Zinc deficiency may be the effect of reduced absorption and can be a contributory factor in disease progression, via the reduction of free radicals. [9] It is known that zinc affects many aspects of the immune system, from the barrier of the skin to gene regulation in lymphocytes, and is crucial for development and function of neutrophils and natural killer cells. [10] There are conflicting published results of zinc levels in patients with CP. [11]

CP is a chronic inflammation of the pancreas triggered by various factors including alcohol misuse, smoking, autoimmunity, anatomical variants and genetic factors. Due to progressive fibrosis and destruction of the pancreas, both enzyme and insulin production ultimately become severely impaired, resulting in pancreatic exocrine and endocrine insufficiency. Deficiency of enzymes (exocrine insufficiency) leads to maldigestion and malnutrition which are associated with reduced absorption of fat-soluble vitamins. The essential role of zinc and its deficiency was described in 1963. [12] Quillot et al [13] have reported that diabetes worsens the antioxidant status in chronic pancreatitis patients.

The aim of the present study was to estimate oxidative stress and antioxidant status in tropical chronic pancreatitis (TCP) and alcoholic chronic pancreatitis (ACP) and correlate with zinc status.

Materials and methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Gastroenterology, Big Apollo Spectra Hospital Patna, Bihar, India and Chronic pancreatitis patients were recruited for the study and was diagnosed on the basis of presence of pancreatic calcification (US/CT) and/or parenchymal or ductal changes on imaging. 100 patients were included in the study. This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee and written informed consent was obtained from the subjects before enrollment. Patients having CP with an alcohol consumption ≥ 80 g/day for at least five years were considered to have ACP while TCP was defined using previously reported criteria. [14]

Diabetes mellitus was diagnosed if the fasting plasma glucose value was equal to or greater than 126 mg/dL, confirmed on two occasions, and/or a plasma glucose value equal to or greater than 200 mg/dL after a 2-hour glucose load confirmed on two occasions, and/or there are requirements for insulin or oral hypoglycemic drugs. [15]

History of illness including presenting complaints, duration of illness, pain and diabetes mellitus, and risk factors, such as alcohol and smoking were recorded. Demographic parameters and anthropometric measurements were elicited and a detailed physical examination was conducted. BMI were calculated by the formula $BMI = \text{weight} / \text{height}^2(\text{kg}/\text{m}^2)$.

Patients with pancreatic cancer, CP patients who had undergone pancreatic surgery, CP patients with complications, like pseudocyst or common bile duct obstruction, or CP patients consuming protein, vitamin, and mineral supplements were excluded.

Fasting blood samples were collected in EDTA tubes and immediately placed in an icebox. Blood samples were centrifuged at 1,000 g for 10 minutes at 4°C. The erythrocytes were carefully sampled from the bottom of the tubes to minimize contamination from leucocytes; they were washed three times with ice-cold isotonic saline solution (1/10 vol/vol) and resuspended in a washing solution to give a 50% solution. Hemolysate obtained were divided into aliquots and stored at -20°C for subsequent enzyme assay. The biochemical tests were performed in the Metabolic Laboratory of the institute. Standard reactions were used to measure the levels of erythrocyte glutathione (GSH) [16], (GPx) [17], SOD [18], TBARS [19], haemoglobin [20] and plasma vitamin C [21] using a UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer (Systronics 2201, Ahmedabad, India). Erythrocyte zinc were

estimated as it provides an assessment of zinc status over a longer period of time as compared to that of the rapidly turning over plasma pool. [22] Erythrocyte lysate was diluted 10-fold with milli-Q water; zinc concentration were determined by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry (3110, Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA). [23]

Statistical analysis was done by using SPSS version 11 software (SPSS Inc, Chicago, USA). Differences

in mean were calculated using one-way analysis of variance with Scheffe post hoc test. Nonparametric Mann

Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis test, as appropriate, was used to compare variables without a normal distribution. Biochemical values were expressed as the mean (SE) for comparison.

Results

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of study population

	Controls (n=50)	Alcoholic pancreatitis (n=50)	Tropical pancreatitis (n=50)
Age (mean [SD])	38 (14.6)	44 (13.7)	36 (14.6)
BMI (mean [SD])	21.6 (3.2)	19.7 (3.4)	19.3 (3.4)
Gender (male:female)	32:18	50:0	36:14
Diabetics	0	27 (54%)	29 (58%)
Smokers	0	41 (82%)	7 (14%)
Pain	0	37 (74%)	41 (82%)

Of the 100 patients, there were 50 TCP patients and 50 ACP patients. The mean age of all CP patients was comparable with the age of controls; however,

TCP patients were younger than ACP patients. The mean body mass index was comparable in all three groups.

Table 2: Blood antioxidant levels and lipid peroxidation product in chronic pancreatitis patients and controls

	Controls	Alcoholic pancreatitis	Tropical pancreatitis
Erythrocyte GSH (µmol/g Hb)	8.52 (0.24)	6.34 (0.22)	5.06 (0.22)
Erythrocyte GPx (nmol of NADPH oxidized/min/g Hb)	19.07 (0.36)	15.44 (0.56)	15.75 (0.46)
Erythrocyte SOD (IU/g Hb)	2974.82 (48.92)	2180.85 (75.35)	2307.63 (85.65)
Erythrocyte TBARS (nmol/g Hb)	5.65 (0.15)	10.2 (0.52)	7.43 (0.32)
Plasma vitamin C (mg/dL)	0.84 (0.07)	0.28 (0.05)	0.4 (0.06)

The erythrocyte GSH, GPx, SOD, and plasma vitamin C levels were lower, and erythrocyte TBARS was higher in both TCP and ACP patients as compared to healthy controls. Plasma vitamin C

was lower whereas, erythrocyte TBARS was higher in TCP patients as compared to ACP patients. Erythrocyte GSH level was significantly low in ACP as compared to TCP patients.

Table 3: Blood antioxidant levels and lipid peroxidation product in diabetic and non-diabetic CP patients and controls (mean [SE])

	Diabetes	Erythrocyte GSH (µmol/g Hb)	Erythrocyte GPx (nmol of NADPH oxidized/min/g Hb)	Erythrocyte SOD (IU/g Hb)	Erythrocyte TBARS (nmol/g Hb)	Plasma vitamin C (mg/dL)
Controls		8.58 (0.22)	19.08 (0.36)	2988.82 (49.96)	5.65 (0.15)	0.84(0.06)
Chronic pancreatitis	Yes	5.40 (0.2)	14.28 (0.37)	2266.44 (64.78)	9.8 (0.39)	0.36(0.04)
	No	5.91 (0.24)	13.97 (0.5)	2278.73 (59.02)	9.02 (0.35)	0.3(0.04)
Tropical pancreatitis	Yes	6.04 (0.36)	14.12 (0.56)	2264.76 (78.31)	11.05 (0.6)	0.28(0.04)
	No	6.51 (0.41)	15.99 (0.82)	2185.01 (92.26)	9.52 (0.6)	0.31(0.06)
Alcoholic	Yes	4.64 (0.16)	14.7 (0.44)	2268.52(108.0)	8.32	0.52(0.09)

pancreatitis				8)	(0.34))
	No	5.38 (0.22)	12.98 (0.55)	2378.62 (72.76)	8.52 (0.37)	0.28(0.06)

We found lower values of erythrocyte GSH, GPx, SOD, and plasma vitamin C and higher erythrocyte TBARS in both diabetic and non-diabetic CP patients as compared to healthy controls. However, we did not find differences between diabetic and non-diabetic TCP patients or between diabetic and non-diabetic ACP patients.

Discussion

Zinc (Zn) is one of the most common trace elements in the human body and plays a substantial role in growth and development, acting as a signaling factor. [24] This metal takes part in the regulation of chronic inflammatory status through the reduction of inflammatory cytokines. Zinc also reduces oxidative stress by participating in the synthesis of antioxidant enzymes and acts as a catalyzer of enzymes, taking part in lipid, carbohydrate, and protein metabolism. It is involved in the synthesis, storage, and release of insulin, which suggests the critical role of this microelement in the progression of type-2 diabetes mellitus, atherosclerosis, and metabolic syndrome (MS). [25-28]

Chronic pancreatitis is a long-standing inflammation of the pancreas that alters the organ's normal structure and functions. [29] It can present as episodes of acute inflammation in a previously injured pancreas, or as chronic damage with persistent pain or malabsorption. It is a disease process characterized by irreversible damage to the pancreas as distinct from reversible changes in acute pancreatitis. Of the 100 patients, there were 50 TCP patients and 50 ACP patients. The mean age of all CP patients was comparable with the age of controls; however, TCP patients were younger than ACP patients. The mean body mass index was comparable in all three groups. The erythrocyte GSH, GPx, SOD, and plasma vitamin C levels were lower, and erythrocyte TBARS was higher in both TCP and ACP patients as compared to healthy controls. Most available data indicate that the primary site for the development of CP is the pancreatic acinar cell. [30] The role of reactive oxygen species (ROS) has been studied in both experimental and human CP. [31,32] ROS play a role in perpetuating the pancreatic inflammation and the development of extra pancreatic complications. [33] However, there is limited literature in identifying oxidant status in tropical chronic pancreatitis (TCP) as compared to alcoholic chronic pancreatitis (ACP). Zinc deficiency has been reported to impact pancreatic function. [34]

Plasma vitamin C was lower whereas, erythrocyte TBARS was higher in TCP patients as compared to ACP patients. Erythrocyte GSH level was

significantly low in ACP as compared to TCP patients. We found lower values of erythrocyte GSH, GPx, SOD, and plasma vitamin C and higher erythrocyte TBARS in both diabetic and non-diabetic CP patients as compared to healthy controls. However, we did not find differences between diabetic and non-diabetic TCP patients or between diabetic and non-diabetic ACP patients. Quillot et al. have reported that diabetes worsens the antioxidant status in CP patients. [35] Braganza et al [36] have suggested the need for region specific antioxidant supplementation.

Conclusion

The study corroborates the role of oxidative stress in CP and suggests some differences in oxidative status in TCP and ACP patients. Zinc deficiency appears to affect oxidative status in CP patients.

References

1. Tasci I, Deveci S, Isik AT, Comert B, Akay C, Mas N, Inal V, Yamanel L, Mas MR. Allopurinol in rat chronic pancreatitis: effects on pancreatic stellate cell activation. *Pancreas*. 2007 Nov 1;35(4):366-71.
2. Vardanyan M, Rilo HL. Pathogenesis of chronic pancreatitis-induced pain. *Discovery Medicine*. 2010 Apr 10;9(47):304-10.
3. Andrén-Sandberg Å, Hoem D, Gislason H. Pain management in chronic pancreatitis. *European journal of gastroenterology & hepatology*. 2002 Sep 1;14(9):957-70.
4. Etemad B, Whitcomb DC. Chronic pancreatitis: diagnosis, classification, and new genetic developments. *Gastroenterology*. 2001 Feb 1;120(3):682-707.
5. Keller J, Layer P. Idiopathic chronic pancreatitis. *Best practice & research Clinical gastroenterology*. 2008 Feb 1;22(1):105-13.
6. Song Y, Leonard SW, Traber MG, Ho E. Zinc deficiency affects DNA damage, oxidative stress, antioxidant defenses, and DNA repair in rats. *J Nutr*. 2009 Sep;139(9):1626-31.
7. Lönnerdal B. Dietary factors influencing zinc absorption. *J Nutr*. 2000 May;130(5S Suppl):1378S-83S.
8. Boosalis MG, Evans GW, McClain CJ. Impaired handling of orally administered zinc in pancreatic insufficiency. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1983 Feb;37(2):268-71.
9. Girish BN, Rajesh G, Vaidyanathan K, Balakrishnan V. Zinc status in chronic pancreatitis and its relationship with exocrine and endocrine insufficiency. *JOP*. 2009 Nov 5; 10(6):651-6.

10. Shankar AH, Prasad AS. Zinc and immune function: the biological basis of altered resistance to infection. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1998 Aug;68(2 Suppl):447S-463S.
11. Lindkvist B, Phillips ME, Domínguez-Muñoz JE. Clinical, anthropometric and laboratory nutritional markers of pancreatic exocrine insufficiency: Prevalence and diagnostic use. *Pancreatol.* 2015 Nov-Dec;15(6):589-97.
12. Song Y, Leonard SW, Traber MG, Ho E. Zinc deficiency affects DNA damage, oxidative stress, antioxidant defenses, and DNA repair in rats. *The Journal of nutrition.* 2009 Sep 1;139(9):1626-31.
13. Quilliot D, Dousset B, Guerci B, Dubois F, Drouin P, Ziegler O. Evidence that diabetes mellitus favors impaired metabolism of zinc, copper, and selenium in chronic pancreatitis. *Pancreas.* 2001 Apr 1;22(3):299-306.
14. Balakrishnan V, Unnikrishnan AG, Thomas V, Choudhuri G, Veeraraju P, Singh SP, Garg P, Pai CG, Devi RN, Bhasin D, Jayanthi V. Chronic pancreatitis. A prospective nationwide study of 1,086 subjects from India. *JOP: Journal of the pancreas.* 2008 Sep 2;9(5):593-6 00.
15. Report of the Expert Committee on the Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes Care.* 1997;20:1183-97.
16. Beutler E, Duron O, Kelly BM. Improved methods for the determination of glutathione. *J Lab Clin Med.* 1963;61:882-8.
17. Paglia DE, Valentine WN. Studies on the quantitative and qualitative characterization of erythrocyte glutathione peroxidase. *J Lab Clin Med.* 1967;70:158-69.
18. Winterbourn CC, Hawkins RE, Brian M, Carrell RW. The estimation of red cell superoxide dismutase activity. *J Lab Clin Med.* 1975;85:337-41.
19. Jain SK, McVie R, Duett J, Herbst JJ. Erythrocyte membrane lipid peroxidation and glycosylated hemoglobin in diabetes. *Diabetes.* 1989;38:1539-43.
20. Drabkins DL, Austin JH. Spectrophotometric constants for common hemoglobin derivatives in human, dog and rabbit blood. *J Biol Chem.* 1932;98:719-33.
21. Okamura M. An improved method for determination of L ascorbic acid and L-dehydroascorbic acid in blood plasma. *Clin Chem Acta.* 1980;103:259-68.
22. Gibson RS, Hess SY, Hotz C, Brown KH. Indicators of zinc status at the population level: a review of the evidence. *Br J Nutr.* 2008; 99 Suppl 3:S14-23.
23. Kenney MA, Ritchey SJ, Culley P, Sandoval W, Moak S, Schilling P. Erythrocyte and dietary zinc in adolescent females. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1984;39:446-51.
24. Hara T, Takeda TA, Takagishi T, Fukue K, Kambe T, Fukada T. Physiological roles of zinc transporters: molecular and genetic importance in zinc homeostasis. *J Physiol Sci.* 2017 Mar;67(2):283-301.
25. Ahn BI, Kim MJ, Koo HS, Seo N, Joo NS, Kim YS. Serum zinc concentration is inversely associated with insulin resistance but not related with metabolic syndrome in nondiabetic Korean adults. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2014 Aug;160(2):169-75.
26. Seo JA, Song SW, Han K, Lee KJ, Kim HN. The associations between serum zinc levels and metabolic syndrome in the Korean population: findings from the 2010 Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *PLoS One.* 2014 Aug 25;9(8):e1059 90.
27. de Oliveira Otto MC, Alonso A, Lee DH, Delclos GL, Jenny NS, Jiang R, Lima JA, Symanski E, Jacobs Jr DR, Nettleton JA. Dietary micronutrient intakes are associated with markers of inflammation but not with markers of subclinical atherosclerosis. *The Journal of nutrition.* 2011 Aug 1;141(8):1508-15.
28. Motamed S, Ebrahimi M, Safarian M, Ghayour-Mobarhan M, Mouhebati M, Azarpazhouh M, Esmailie H, Norouzi A, Ferns GA. Micronutrient intake and the presence of the metabolic syndrome. *N Am J Med Sci.* 2013 Jun;5(6):377-85.
29. Chronic pancreatitis: Medline Plus Medical Encyclopedia. www.nlm.nih.gov. Retrieved 2015-11-29.
30. Chvanov M, Petersen OH, Tepikin A. Free radicals and the pancreatic acinar cells: role in physiology and pathology. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences.* 2005 Dec 29;360(1464):273-84.
31. Braganza JM, Dormandy TL. Micronutrient therapy for chronic pancreatitis: rationale and impact. *JOP. Journal of the Pancreas.* 2010 Mar 5;11(2):99-112.
32. Verlaan M, Roelofs HM, van Schaik A, Wanten GJ, Jansen JB, Peters WH, Drenth JP. Assessment of oxidative stress in chronic pancreatitis patients. *World Journal of Gastroenterology: WJG.* 2006 Sep 9;12(35):5705.
33. Leung PS, Chan YC. Role of oxidative stress in pancreatic inflammation. *Antioxidants & redox signaling.* 2009 Jan 1;11(1):135-66.
34. Matsumura N, Ochi K, Ichimura M, Mizushima T, Harada H, Harada M. Study on free radicals and pancreatic fibrosis—pancreatic fibrosis induced by repeated injections of superoxide dismutase inhibitor. *Pancreas.* 2001 Jan 1; 22(1):53-7.
35. Quilliot D, Walters E, Bonte JP, Fruchart JC, Duriez P, Ziegler O. Diabetes mellitus worsens antioxidant status in patients with chronic pan-

creatitis. The American journal of clinical nutrition. 2005 May 1;81(5):1117-25.
36. Braganza JM, Schofield D, Snehalatha C, Mohan V. Micronutrient antioxidant status in

tropical compared with temperate-zone chronic pancreatitis. Scandinavian journal of gastroenterology. 1993 Jan 1;28(12):1098-104.